

Biomedical Research Co-authorship Network Analysis utilizing Machine Learning Models

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Abstract

Social network analysis is a graph-based method for visualizing social networks. In this study, co-authorship patterns were analyzed within the Center of Biomedical Research Excellence in Matrix Biology based on peer-reviewed journal publications by center members. The data set included 200 articles published by 664 individual authors from 2014 to October 2022. The purpose of the study was to investigate the growth pattern of the biomedical research program utilizing bibliometric data. Network analysis may allow an understanding of the factors that determine the success of research programs. Pearson's correlation coefficients and machine learning models were used to investigate the relationship strength and predictions of future center behavior. Pearson's correlation indicated that co-authorship network visualization and analysis may be a useful tool to understand the relationship between a research center and research productivity of investigators. The predictive models may help to identify variables that are accurate predictors of future behavior.

Key Words: Center of Biomedical Research Excellence, COBRE, co-authorship network, Deep Neural Network, machine learning.

1. Introduction

Social network analysis (SNA) relies on a collection of methods and tools to study the relationships, interactions, and communication in a network¹. SNA can be used to identify patterns of relationships among people in groups, to investigate social structures, and to characterize networked structures in terms of nodes and edges. Nodes represent individuals within the network and the connection between the nodes are referred to as edges (Fig. 1). Edges may be weighted according to degree, or the total number of connections to other nodes. Thicker edges may be used to represent higher degree nodes. Nodes may also be sized to reflect specific attributes as well.

Fig. 1: Structure of a Social Network Analysis representing Nodes (blue colored circles) and Edges (cyan colored straight line). Nodes represent individuals within the network and the connection between the nodes are referred to as Edges. Bigger Nodes indicate more individuals and thicker Edges indicate more connections in a Social Network Analysis.

Mathematically, the social network is a graph determined by the equation

$$G = (N, E)$$

where N represents the node, and E represents the edge (see figure above). Edges may be directed or undirected. For example, Facebook can be described with an undirected graph since the friendship is bidirectional, “person A” and “person B” being friends is the same as “person B” and “person A” being friends². On the other hand, Twitter can be described with a directed graph: “person A” can follow “person B” without “person B” following “person A”².

In this study, network centrality in a co-authorship network was analyzed. Network centrality methods may be used as a metric to identify important nodes within a network³. Our research is aimed at understanding the collaborative network within COBRE in Matrix Biology at an emerging research institution using SNA. A study was conducted between 2014 and 2022 to assess the levels of connectivity among authors of peer-reviewed publications that acknowledge the COBRE in Matrix Biology grant (P20GM109095).

2. Data Pre-processing

Data pre-processing included the conversion of raw data into data formatted for the subsequent analysis. Fig. 2 outlines the pre-processing steps used for this study.

Fig. 2: Data pre-processing diagram of the biomedical co-authorship network analysis under COBRE in Matrix Biology funding from 2014 – 2022. Data collection from PubMed (Biomedical co-authorship network data was collected from PubMed⁵ website under COBRE in Matrix Biology funding from 2014 to 2022). MEDLINE text file generation (A MEDLINE text file was generated from the PubMed⁵ website including P20GM109095-cited papers from 2014 to 2022). Master thesaurus file creation (A master thesaurus was created to resolve duplication of authors’ publishing names). Creating a compatible data file (Data has been modified into an excel format using Gephi⁶ software to perform analysis effectively). Model compilation (Machine learning models were compiled to predict the future trends of the co-authorship patterns under COBRE in the Matrix Biology network from 2014 to 2022).

2.1 Data collection from PubMed:

PubMed.gov⁵ was used to collect data with the search term P20GM109095 to identify publications related to the center from 2014 to October 2022.

2.2 Data Formation:

Data formation included the following steps of pre-processing shown in Fig. 2: 1) MEDLINE text file generation, 2) Creating a master thesaurus, and 3) Generating a compatible excel file.

1) MEDLINE text file generation:

From the National Library of Medicine website PubMed⁵ P20GM109095-cited papers from 2014 to October 2022 were included in the MEDLINE text file.

2) Master thesaurus file creation:

A master thesaurus was created to resolve duplication of authors who have more than one publishing name. Using VOSviewer⁷ software, a master thesaurus file was generated after inputting the MEDLINE text file.

3) Creating a compatible data file:

VOSviewer software was used to process the MEDLINE text file with the master thesaurus. Gephi software was used to collect the statistical outputs related to our data. Gephi is an open-source software for visualizing and analyzing large network graphs⁶. Excel and a CSV format were used for further analysis.

3. Model Compilation

The purpose of predictive modeling is to predict future behavior, activity, and trends based upon current and historical data. To predict the future trends of the co-authorship patterns within the NIH Center of Biomedical Research Excellence (COBRE) in the Matrix Biology network, the correlation matrix plot (Fig. 3) was considered and used to identify the related variables.

Fig. 3: Pearson's Correlation Matrix of COBRE during 2014 – 2022 showcasing Eigen centrality (Eigen centrality is a measure of node importance in a network based on a node's connections), Triangles (A triangle is a set of three nodes where each node has a relationship to the other two), Page ranks (An iterative algorithm that measures the importance of each node within the network), Weight links (Weight link is considered as the total number of edges per author), Weight total link strength (Weight total link strength attribute indicates the total strength of the co-authorship links of a given researcher with other researchers), Weight documents (It represents the total number of papers per author), Degree (How many edges are adjacent to a node determines its degree), Weighted Degree (The larger the degree, the heavier the node is weighted. Nodes were weighted based on the number of publications), Betweenness Centrality (A node's position on a shortest path between nodes in a network is called its betweenness centrality) of the biomedical co-authorship network data under COBRE in matrix Biology funding from 2014 – 2022. All these variables are good predictors for predicting Hub (Hubs are defined as nodes with more edges than the average node within the network and may be located centrally, facilitating traffic over the network).

The correlation matrix plot indicated that 'Hub' had strong correlation with 'eigen centrality', 'triangles', 'pageranks', 'weight links', 'weight total link strength', 'weight documents', 'degree', 'weighted degree', and 'betweenness centrality'. These variables were used as predictors of future behaviors of nodes within the network. Seven different machine learning models for regression were compared for their performance on prediction of the future behavior. The machine learning models used were 1) Deep Neural Network, 2) k-nearest neighbors, 3) decision tree, 4) random

forest, 5) multivariate linear regression, 6) support vector machine, and 7) ensemble learning: stacking. Comparison of these models is described below.

3.1 Deep Neural Networks

A deep neural network (DNN) is a branch of data science that focuses on algorithms based on the biological structure of the human brain. DNN learns high-level features incrementally from data. DNN eliminates the need for domain expertise and hard-core feature extraction. As a result, a DNN model was chosen to make predictions from the dataset. More specifically, a Deep Neural Network Tensorflow Keras model was compiled using the following hyperparameters rectified linear unit (ReLU) and linear activation functions, Mean Square Error loss function, adam optimizer with 0.0001 learning rate, 5 layers including the input layer with 64 dense and the output layer with 1 dense, and 100 epochs. In terms of DNN an epoch refers to one cycle through the full training dataset. Similarly, if epoch is 20, it means that 20 cycles through the full training dataset.

Fig. 4: (a) Actual vs predicted plot of Hubs (Hubs are defined as nodes with more edges than the average node within the network and may be located centrally, facilitating traffic over the network) deploying a Deep Neural Network model for regression considering Eigen centrality (Eigen centrality is a measure of node importance in a network based on a node's connections), Triangles (A triangle is a set of three nodes where each node has a relationship to the other two), Page ranks (An iterative algorithm that measures the importance of each node within the network), Weight links (Weight link is considered as the total number of edges per author), Weight total link strength (Weight total link strength attribute indicates the total strength of the co-authorship links of a given researcher with other researchers), Weight document (Weight document represents the total number of papers per author), Degree (How many edges are adjacent to a node determines its degree), Weighted Degree (The larger the degree, the heavier the node is weighted. Nodes were weighted based on the number of publications), Betweenness Centrality (A node's position on a shortest path between nodes in a network is called its betweenness centrality) of the biomedical co-authorship network data under COBRE in matrix Biology funding from 2014 – 2022. (b) DNN model loss by training epochs of the biomedical data under COBRE in matrix Biology funding from 2014 - 2022.

The Fig. 4(a) shows the actual vs. predicted plot of 'Hub' deploying the Deep Neural Network Tensorflow Keras model for regression considering 'eigen centrality', 'triangles', 'pageranks', 'weight links', 'weight total link strength', 'weight documents', 'degree', 'weighted degree', 'betweenness centrality' of the bibliometric data from 2014 – 2022. Each point on the plot represented a node. According to the Fig. 4(a), most of the nodes followed the linear trend indicating that 'eigen centrality', 'triangles', 'pageranks', 'weight links', 'weight total link strength', 'weight documents', 'degree', 'weighted degree', 'betweenness centrality' variables were correlated with 'Hub'. Based on the model evaluation metrics, the root mean square error was 0.00089 and the mean absolute error was 0.00057. The adjusted coefficient of determination (adj R-square) considering the bibliometric dataset and prediction dataset indicated that the DNN model predicted the Hub 99.950% accurately. The model loss by training epoch (Fig. 4(b)), indicated that both training loss and validation loss decreased to stability at $y = 0$. Furthermore, the predictions were adequately matched with the actual Hub, suggesting the model was a success.

3.2 k-Nearest Neighbors (k-NN):

A k-NN model was evaluated and resulted in an adjusted R-square value of 99.351% indicating that the k-NN model predicted the Hub data 99.351% accurately. The model evaluation metrics root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) were 0.00320 and 0.00163, respectively. Actual Hub versus prediction plot (Fig. 5(a)) showed a linear trend with a little off trend behavior of some nodes.

3.3 Decision Tree:

The performance of the random forest model provided a linear trend between the actual vs predicted Hub (Fig. 5(b)) with one outlier. The model prediction was 99.375% accurate (according to the adjusted R square of test and predicted values of Hub). While 99.375% adjusted R–square indicated that the data fit accuracy was high, the low RMSE value (0.00314) and the low MAE value (0.00062) indicated a good predictive model as well.

Fig. 5: Hubs (Hubs are defined as nodes with more edges than the average node within the network and may be located centrally, facilitating traffic over the network) actual vs prediction using (a) k nearest neighbors, (b) Decision Tree, (c) Random Forest, (d) Linear Regression, (e) Support Vector Regressor, (f) Ensemble Learning: Stacking of the biomedical data under COBRE in matrix Biology funding from 2014 – 2022.

3.4 Random Forest Model:

A comparatively better model performance came from the random forest model. The 99.841% adjusted R-square value (Fig. 5c) indicated that the model’s prediction percentage evaluation predicted Hub values very adequately. The random forest model showcased low RMSE (0.00158) and low MAE (0.00056) values which fulfilled the goal of a good predictive model.

3.5 Multivariate Linear Regression:

The multivariate linear regression model predicted the Hub data adequately (Fig. 5d). It formed a linear trend with no outliers. It had the second highest adjusted R-square value (99.968%). The RMSE 0.00071 and MAE 0.00059 were giving us comparatively the 2nd low values. These values indicated that their evaluation of prediction performances met the basic adequate model performance expectations.

3.6 Support Vector Regressor (SVR):

The support vector regression model (Fig. 5e) resulted the lowest adjusted R-square value -3.77609 and the highest RMSE 0.08681 and MAE 0.08601 values which pointed to this approach being a poor predicted model for Hub dataset. We should avoid this model to predict the Hub.

3.7 Ensemble Learning - Stacking:

For this approach, five different models were stacked: k-nearest neighbors, random forest, decision tree, SVR and linear regression together to model the Hub dataset. The average output from this ensemble model stacking approach was considered (Fig. 5f). The goal was to achieve better model performance as well as better prediction. This ensemble technique resulted the best R-square value, 99.969% which indicated that the ensemble stacking approach

fitted the Hub dataset accurately. The RMSE (0.00069) and MAE (0.00057) values were comparatively the lowest. When the k-nearest neighbors, random forest, decision tree, and linear regression models were used individually, good prediction performance accuracies were acquired with higher RMSE and MAE values. The SVR model failed to meet the model expectation regarding the Hub related dataset. This ensemble stacking approach provided the best result.

The results of the model comparison were summarized in the table below.

Table 1: Comparison summary of different machine learning models for regression to predict Hubs (Hubs are defined as nodes with more edges than the average node within the network and may be located centrally, facilitating traffic over the network) considering Eigen centrality (Eigen centrality is a measure of node importance in a network based on a node's connections), Triangles (A triangle is a set of three nodes where each node has a relationship to the other two), Page ranks (An iterative algorithm that measures the importance of each node within the network), Weight links (Weight link is considered as the total number of edges per author), Weight total link strength (Total link strength attribute indicates the total strength of the co-authorship links of a given researcher with other researchers), Weight documents (It represents the total number of papers per author), Degree (How many edges are adjacent to a node determines its degree), Weighted degree (The larger the degree, the heavier the node is weighted. Nodes were weighted based on the number of publications), Betweenness centrality (A node's position on a shortest path between nodes in a network is called its betweenness centrality) of the biomedical co-authorship network data under COBRE in matrix Biology funding from 2014 – 2022.

	DNN	k-NN	Decision Tree	Random Forest	Multivariate Linear Regression	Support Vector Regressor	Ensemble Learning: Stacking
Adj R2	0.99950	0.99351	0.99375	0.99841	0.99968	-3.77609	0.99969
RMSE	0.00089	0.00320	0.00314	0.00158	0.00071	0.08681	0.00069
MAE	0.00057	0.00163	0.00062	0.00056	0.00059	0.08601	0.00057

Table 1 showcases the better machine learning model performance in an ascending order. Ensemble Learning: Stacking model > Multivariate Linear Regression > DNN > Random Forest > Decision Tree > k-NN. There was good agreement between all these machine learning models and the dataset since all the data points (blue color points in Fig. 4(a) and Fig. 5(a, b, c, d, and f)) were on the 45 degree angel straight line. The performance of the Support Vector Regression model (Fig. 5(e)) failed to live up to the modeling expectations.

4. Conclusion:

The objective of this study was to apply social network analysis tools to better understand the collaborative network within the COBRE in Matrix Biology. We investigated the connectivity of authors of peer-reviewed publications that acknowledged the COBRE in Matrix Biology grant (P20GM109095) during the time period between 2014 to 2022 representing 200 publications, and 664 unique authors. Among those authors, 16 core staff and 47 COBRE investigators were evaluated using SNA techniques. With the blessing of social network analysis, we identified the best predictors of Hub were eigen centrality and triangle variables based on their strong connectivity. The correlation matrix plot (Fig. 3) revealed that 'Hub' also had meaningful connections with 'pageranks', 'weight links', 'weight total link strength', 'weight documents', 'degree', 'weighted degree', and 'betweenness centrality'. Our results yielded the model performance sequence as Ensemble Learning: Stacking model > Multivariate Linear Regression > DNN > Random Forest > Decision Tree > k-NN. The performance of the support vector regression model (SVR) failed to live up to the modeling expectations. It might be asserted that the COBRE in the Matrix Biology Biomolecular Research Center acted as a central Hub supporting the culture of shared core facilities and collaborations fostering

increased co-authorship incidences. In addition, these machine learning models could help predict future new COBRE Matrix Biology researchers.

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